

The Influence of Work Engagement and Proactive Personality on Employee Performance at PT Kilang Pertamina Internasional Refinery Unit III Plaju

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ABSTRACT: This study aims to analyze the influence of work engagement and proactive personality on employee performance. The sample in this study were 210 employees of PT Kilang Pertamina Internasional RU III production unit. The analysis method used was Structural Equation Modeling (SEM). The results showed that Work Engagement had a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance. Proactive Personality had a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance. These findings indicate that high work engagement and a proactive personality contribute directly to improved individual performance in the oil and gas industry. This research strengthens the Social Exchange Theory, that a positive reciprocal relationship between individuals and organizations can encourage productive and results-oriented work behavior.

KEYWORDS: Work Engagement, Proactive Personality, Employee Performance

INTRODUCTION

Employee performance is an important indicator in assessing the effectiveness and competitiveness of a company, especially in strategic sectors such as the oil refining industry. In improving performance, there must be high employee work involvement and concern for their work in order to provide good performance results (Sayekti, 2024). This raises the need to re-evaluate psychological factors and work behavior which may play an important role, such as work engagement and proactive personality. Both are seen as non-technical factors capable of encouraging employee initiative, commitment, and the quality of contributions in a more comprehensive and sustainable manner. In other words, even though technical and procedural aspects have been implemented systematically, achieving optimal performance seems to require an approach that touches more on the personal and motivational dimensions of employees. Research by (Corbeanu & Iliescu, 2023) Research shows that work engagement significantly correlates with performance, both in terms of completing core tasks and contributing outside of formal work. Engaged employees tend to demonstrate high performance because they work with enthusiasm, focus, and a strong commitment to results. According to (Bakker & Leiter, 2010) Work engagement is a satisfying and positive work state, as well as a feeling of motivation in working, which can be seen as the opposite of work fatigue (burnout), so that in carrying out work employees will be enthusiastic and have a high energy level. According to (Bakker & Leiter, 2010) Work engagement has broad implications for employee performance and can even support additional employee performance. The energy and focus inherent in work engagement enable employees to bring their full potential to their work. This inherent energy and focus are qualities at the core of their responsibilities. They have the capacity and motivation to concentrate exclusively on the task at hand.

Besides work engagement, proactive personality is also a factor that influences employee performance. According to (Bakker & Demerouti, 2012) Proactive personality is a structure that captures behavioral tendencies to identify and change one's environment. Proactive personality is described as individuals who are active in their work, especially in adapting to their environment. Therefore, individuals with a proactive type are said to be more likely to be successful in their work in the future. Proactive people tend to seize opportunities, take initiative, act boldly, and are determined to create value-added change. Proactive personality is an individual characteristic that shows a tendency to act with initiative, anticipate problems, and create positive changes in the environment (Anugrahito, 2021). Study by (Köksal et al., 2023) revealed that proactive personality is positively correlated with innovative behavior, problem-solving, and ultimately job performance. Proactive personality It is crucial to maintaining an organization's competitive advantage in today's rapidly changing environment. A proactive personality can produce a variety of beneficial outcomes, including improved task performance, increased creativity, and professional success. (X. Yang & Chau, 2021). Proactive individuals always seek opportunities, take initiative, and persevere until goals are achieved. Some

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individuals tend to have a positive attitude, while others are more passive and lack a strong desire to contribute to organizational change. This significantly impacts employee performance. (Mustika & Susanto, 2022).

Previous studies that examined the influence of work engagement on employee performance were conducted by (H. Putri & Utami, 2025); (Sayekti, 2024); (Puspa & Wibowo, 2023); (Bakker, 2022); (Syarifah, 2021); (Manalu, 2021) showed that work engagement had a positive and significant effect on employee performance. Different results were shown by research from (Satiti, 2023) and (Kustya, 2020) showed that work engagement had a positive but insignificant effect on employee performance. Meanwhile, the research results from (Vernanda, 2025) shows that the work environment has a negative and insignificant effect on employee performance. The influence of proactive personality factors also affects employee performance. The results of research conducted by (Syafitri, 2023); (Bakker, 2022); (Chen, 2022); (Hu, 2021); (C. Yang, 2020) and (JB Fuller, 2020) shows that proactive personality has a positive and significant influence on employee performance. The results of the study from (Anugrahito, 2021) shows that proactive personality has a positive and insignificant effect on employee performance.

Based on the description above, the main problem that will be discussed in this research is how the influence of work engagement and proactive personality on employee performance at PT Kilang Pertamina Internasional Refinery Unit III Plaju? Then the objective to be achieved in this study is to find empirical evidence by analyzing the influence of work engagement and proactive personality on employee performance at PT Kilang Pertamina Internasional Refinery Unit III Plaju.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Work Engagement

According to (Bakker & Leiter, 2010) Work engagement is a satisfying and positive work state, as well as a feeling of motivation in working which can be seen as the opposite of work fatigue (burnout) so that in doing work employees will be enthusiastic and have a high level of energy. Work engagement is a characteristic of a sense of commitment, having a great desire and enthusiasm, which brings efforts to a higher level, continues to work hard, and has initiative. (Andrian & Sabeli, 2020).

According to (Bakker & Leiter, 2010), states that there are three dimensions in measuring work engagement, including:

1. Vigor

Vigor is the enthusiasm an individual feels when performing a task. It reflects a person's energy level and mental resilience while working. Furthermore, vigor also indicates an employee's willingness to exert significant effort to complete a task, resisting fatigue easily, even when experiencing difficulties.

2. Dedication

Dedication is an employee's strong involvement in their work. Employee engagement is a positive feeling, such as enthusiasm for completing work and a sense of attachment to their job and the company they work for.

3. Absorption

Absorption is the full concentration that employees have in doing their work where employees feel that when they are doing their work, time seems to pass so quickly because they enjoy their work and it is difficult to let go of themselves when doing their work because they feel comfortable with the work they are doing.

Proactive Personality

Proactive personality is an attitude that tends to take advantage of opportunities, dares to take action in deciding something and is active in carrying out the work being done (Suryani, 2020). According to (Bakker & Demerouti, 2012), proactive personality is a structure that captures behavioral tendencies to identify and change one's environment.

According to (Bateman & Crant, 1999) and (Mahardika & Kistyanto, 2020) The proactive personality dimension is divided into several types, including:

1. Ability to See Opportunities

The ability to spot opportunities is a unique skill, requiring continuous practice to master. However, this ability is not shared equally by everyone, as people have different orientations to space and time. Individuals with this ability will readily seize opportunities, thus potentially acting more quickly than others.

2. Initiative

Initiative is a person's ability to generate ideas for doing a task without being told what to do first. Someone with this ability is naturally resourceful and likely to relentlessly learn and develop themselves.

3. Taking Action

Taking action is a behavioral alternative from two or more available alternatives. Taking action is the process of choosing or determining various possibilities among uncertain situations. Therefore, taking action is driven by an idea or thought.

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Performance

Performance according to (Dessler, 2020) is work performance, namely the comparison between the work results achieved by a person with the work standards set by the company. Work results that can be achieved by a person or group of people in an organization, in accordance with their respective authorities and responsibilities in order to achieve the goals of the organization concerned legally, without violating the law and in accordance with morals and ethics. Success or failure in an organization in carrying out tasks is closely related to employee performance, performance achievement in the organization is a factor that must be considered to realize the company in achieving the goals that have been set. (Silitonga, 2023).

According to (Robbins & Judge, 2019), there are six dimensions for measuring individual employee performance, namely:

1. Quality

Work quality is measured by employee perceptions of the quality of work produced and the perfection of tasks relative to employee skills and abilities. Work quality can be described by the level of good or bad employee performance in completing tasks, as well as employee abilities and skills in carrying out assigned tasks.

2. Quantity

Quantity is the amount produced, expressed in terms such as the number of units or the number of activity cycles completed. Quantity is a measure of the number of units of work produced or the number of activity cycles completed by an employee, so employee performance can be measured by these numbers (units/cycles). For example, an employee can complete their work quickly, ahead of the company's deadline.

3. Punctuality

Punctuality is the degree to which an activity is completed at the stated start time, in terms of coordination with output results and maximizing the time available for other activities. Employee performance can also be measured by the employee's punctuality in completing assigned work, ensuring that it does not interfere with other work within their scope of duties.

4. Effectiveness

Effectiveness is the degree to which an organization's resources (human resources, money, technology, and raw materials) are maximized with the aim of increasing the output of each unit. This means that employees can utilize resources, whether human resources themselves or resources in the form of technology, capital, information, and raw materials, to the maximum extent possible.

5. Independence

Independence is the degree to which an employee will be able to carry out their work functions and work commitments. This is the level at which employees have a work commitment to the agency and employee responsibilities to the office. The improvement or decline of employee performance can be seen from the quality of employee work, the quantity of employee work, the employee's punctuality in all aspects of work, the employee's effectiveness and independence in working. This means that an independent employee is an employee who does not need supervision when doing his work and can carry out his work functions independently without asking for help, guidance from others or supervisors.

Research Conceptual Framework

Based on the reference review and theoretical basis, as well as previous research, a conceptual framework can be developed that underpins this research and the influence of independent and dependent variables. This conceptual framework is expected to provide benefits, namely, a shared perception between researchers and readers regarding the research flow.

Figure 1. Research Conceptual Framework

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Hypothesis

According to (Bakker & Leiter, 2010) Work engagement is a satisfying and positive work state, as well as a feeling of motivation in working, which can be seen as the opposite of work exhaustion (burnout), so that in doing the job employees will be enthusiastic and have a high energy level. Work engagement relates to all types of challenging work. It describes the ability of employees to bring their full capacity to solve problems, relate to people and develop innovative management services that make a difference. Also, employees' responses to policies, practices and organizational structures affect their potential to experience engagement. In a stable work environment, employees maintain a high level of work engagement together. (Imawati, 2021). Based on Social Exchange Theory (SET) (Blau, 1964), The relationship between employees and organizations is reciprocal, where employees who feel treated fairly and supported by the organization will respond with positive behaviors such as higher work engagement. As a form of reciprocity, this engagement then translates into improved work performance. This means that when employees feel valued and supported, they will be more emotionally, cognitively, and physically engaged in their tasks, which ultimately increases productivity and work quality. This finding is supported by a number of empirical studies in the past five years. Research by (Putra & Suhermin, 2020) shows that work engagement has a positive and significant influence on employee performance in the energy sector. A similar finding was also found in research by (DW Putri, 2022) which shows that work engagement positively mediates the relationship between leadership and employee performance. Furthermore, a study by Rahmawati and Hidayat (2023) revealed that the vigor, dedication, and absorption aspects of work engagement directly contribute to increased work effectiveness and the achievement of organizational targets. According to (Bakker & Leiter, 2010) Work engagement has broad implications for employee performance and can even support additional employee performance. The energy and focus inherent in work engagement enable employees to bring their full potential to their work. This inherent energy and focus are qualities at the core of their responsibilities. They have the capacity and motivation to concentrate exclusively on the task at hand.

H1 :Work Engagement has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance

According to (Bakker & Demerouti, 2012) Proactive personality is a structure that captures behavioral tendencies to identify and change one's environment. Proactive personality is described as individuals who are active in their work, especially in adapting to the environment. Therefore, individuals with a proactive type are said to be more likely to be successful in their work in the future. Proactive people tend to seize opportunities, take initiative, act boldly, and are determined to create value-added change. (Wati & Suryani, 2021) A proactive personality is crucial for maintaining an organization's competitive advantage in today's rapidly changing environment. A proactive personality can produce a variety of beneficial outcomes, including improved task performance, increased creativity, and professional success. (X. Yang & Chau, 2021) Proactive individuals always seek opportunities, take initiative, and persevere until goals are achieved. Some individuals tend to have a positive attitude, while others are more passive and lack a strong desire to contribute to organizational change. This significantly impacts employee performance. (Mustika & Susanto, 2022). Study by (Anwar & Febrianti, 2021) shows that proactive personality has a significant influence on the achievement of work targets and the effectiveness of task completion. Furthermore, research by (Wijaya & Handayani, 2022) Research in the oil and gas industry shows that employees with a proactive personality adapt more quickly to operational changes and are more efficient at work. Other research by (Nugroho & Lestari, 2023) also emphasized that proactive personality increases an individual's perception of control over work, which ultimately has a positive impact on work output.

H2 :Proactive Personality has a positive and significant influence on Employee Performance

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In this study, the population was all employees of PT Kilang Pertamina Internasional Refinery Unit III Plaju, production division with permanent employee status, totaling 440 employees. who have 1–10 years of service, along with their direct supervisors. The sample in this study was taken from the entire population. employees with permanent employee status PT Kilang Pertamina Internasional Refinery Unit III Plaju production department in 2025. The sample determination from the population number is based on calculations using the Slovin formula so that a sample of 210 employees is obtained including the CDL Unit (Crude Distiller & Light End) as many as 44 people, the PP Unit (Polypropylene) as many as 60 people, the UTL Unit (Utilities) as many as 46 people and the OM Unit (Oil Movement) as many as 60 people. The analysis technique in this study uses regression using the SEM PLS application through testing the outer model and inner model.

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RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Outer Model

1. Discriminant Validity Test
 - a. Fornell–Larcker Criterion

Table 1. Fornell-Lacker Criterion of Cognitive Testing

Construct	Employee Performance	Work Engagement	Proactive Personality
Employee performance	0.877		
Work Engagement	0.615		0.900
Proactive Personality	0.643	0.899	0.317

These results indicate that each construct has a greater shared variance with its own indicators compared to other constructs. In other words, each variable in the research model—Work Engagement, Proactive Personality, and Employee Performance—has a distinct identity and does not overlap empirically. This finding aligns with the criteria proposed by (Fornell & Larcker, 1981) which states that discriminant validity is met when the VAVE of each construct is greater than the correlation between constructs.

- b. Heterotrait–Monotrait Ratio (HTMT)

Table 2. Heterotrait-Monotrait Testing (HTMT)

Construct	Employee performance	Proactive Personality	Work Engagement
Employee performance	—		
Proactive Personality	0.656	—	
Work Engagement	0.627	0.322	—

All HTMT values obtained were well below the threshold of 0.90, which means that there is no excessive relationship between constructs in the model.

2. Reliability and Average Variance Extracted (AVE) Testing

Table 3. Reliability and Average Variance Extracted (AVE) Testing

	Cronbach's alpha	Composite reliability (rho_a)	Composite reliability (rho_c)	Average variance extracted (AVE)
Employee performance	0.979	0.979	0.980	0.769
Proactive Personality	0.974	0.975	0.977	0.810
Work Engagement	0.973	0.975	0.977	0.808

Based on table 4, it can be seen that all constructs have Cronbach's Alpha and Composite reliability (rho_a) values > 0.7 and all AVE values > 0.5, so it can be said that all constructs are reliable.

Inner Model

1. R Square

Table 4. R Square Test

	R-square	R-square adjusted
Performance	0.602	0.598

Based on the analysis results, the R² value for the Employee Performance variable (Y) was 0.602, meaning that 60.2% of the variation in employee performance can be explained by the combination of Work Engagement and Proactive Personality. The remaining 39.8% is explained by other factors outside the model, such as the work environment, leadership, and the organization's performance appraisal system. According to (Chin, 1998) in (Ghozali, 2021), an R² value of 0.33–0.67 is categorized as a strong to moderate model. Thus, the structural model in this study is categorized as strong, as both independent variables are able to substantially explain employee performance.

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2. F Square

Table 5. F Square Test

	Performance	Proactive Personality	Work Engagement
Performance			
Proactive Personality	0.561		
Work Engagement	0.473		

The f^2 value shows that both variables have a large influence on employee performance (> 0.35), meaning that both work engagement and proactive personality have a substantive contribution to improving employee performance.

3. Predictive Relevance (Q^2)

Table 6. Testing Predictive Relevance (Q^2)

	SSO	SSE	$Q^2 (=1-SSE/SSO)$
Performance	3150	1712.77	0.456
Proactive Personality	2100	2100	
Work Engagement	2100	2100	

Based on the calculation results, a Q^2 value of 0.456 was obtained, indicating the model has good predictive capability. Since the Q^2 value is > 0 , this indicates that the combination of Work Engagement and Proactive Personality is able to predict employee performance relevantly.

4. Goodness of Fit (GoF) and Model Fit

Table 7. Goodness of Fit (GoF) and Model Fit Test

	Saturated Model	Estimated Model
SRMR	0.037	0.037
d_ ULS	0.859	0.859
d_ G	0.963	0.963
Chi-Square	1015,226	1015,226
NFI	0.897	0.897

The results of the Goodness of Fit (GoF) calculation show a value of 0.692, which is included in the large fit category. (Ghozali, 2021). This indicates that the overall research model has a high fit between the measurement model and the structural model. Furthermore, the Standardized Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR) value of 0.037 also indicates a good fit, as the SRMR value is < 0.10 (Henseler et al., 2014). Thus, the research model can be said to have a good level of fit and accuracy in explaining the phenomena of relationships between variables.

5. Hypothesis Testing

Table 8. Hypothesis Testing

	T statistics ($ O/STDEV $)	P values
Work Engagement \rightarrow Performance	0.241	0.809
Proactive Personality \rightarrow Performance	10,772	0.000

The results of the analysis show:

This study found that Work Engagement has a positive and significant influence on Employee Performance (p -value = $0.000 < 0.05$; $\beta = 0.457$; $t = 6.748$). The higher the level of work engagement perceived by employees, the higher their performance. This finding is supported by Social Exchange Theory (SET), which explains that a positive reciprocal relationship between an organization and employees fosters a sense of responsibility and commitment, which results in greater energy, dedication, and work absorption from employees. These results are in line with research by (Bakker & Demerouti, 2018; Schaufeli, 2021) which states that engaged employees tend to have superior performance due to the positive psychological conditions they experience, such as being more energetic, focused, and strongly committed.

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Proactive Personality was found to have a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance ($\beta = 0.498$; $t = 7.650$; $p\text{-value} = 0.000 < 0.05$). This indicates that individuals with a proactive personality have a greater tendency to take initiatives, seek solutions, and adapt to job demands and changes, thereby improving their work performance. This finding supports Social Exchange Theory (SET), where employee proactive behavior is seen as a form of reciprocity for the support and trust provided by the organization. The results of this study are also consistent with the findings (CM Fuller & Marler, 2022), which confirms that proactive personality is a strong predictor of innovative work behavior and individual effectiveness, especially in dynamic industrial environments such as the oil and gas sector.

CONCLUSIONS, LIMITATIONS, AND SUGGESTIONS

Based on the analysis, it can be concluded that work engagement has a positive and significant effect on employee performance. Proactive personality has a positive and significant effect on employee performance. Work engagement and proactive personality are able to explain 60.2% of the variation in employee performance, indicating that psychological and personality factors have a significant contribution to work performance in the oil and gas industry, which highly demands discipline, safety, and high adaptability.

Although it meets the standards of empirical analysis, this study has several limitations that need to be considered. Data collection was conducted over a limited time period (cross-sectional), so it is not able to describe changes in employee behavior longitudinally. For future research, a longitudinal or time-lagged design is recommended to more accurately capture the dynamics of changes in engagement and performance.

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